

Deanship of Graduate Studies

Journalism Specialization

Applications of Game Theory in the Russian– Ukrainian Crisis

Prepared by/ Hassan Mohammed Al–Baiti

Master of Journalism

Supervised by Dr. Youssef Kouriye

Lecturer at the École Supérieure de Journalisme de Paris

2022

Introduction

International relations contributed positively to the Russian-Ukrainian war from political and economic angles to some countries, and in turn there was a negative side to other countries.

Therefore, the role of international relations in the Russian-Ukrainian crisis is not the result of the moment, and international interference in it is the same, so it should be studied from three things:

- 1- Factors affecting international relations that played a role in the crisis
- 2- The study of power and war in those factors
- 3- Studying the phenomenon of international cooperation with both warring parties on Ukrainian territory

In order to pave the way for talking about the factors affecting international relations that played a role in this crisis, we will address important concepts that will help us later to understand this conflict. The most prominent of these concepts are:

- 1- International relations: It is a phenomenon of overlapping political and non-political mutual interactions between the various units of the international community.
- 2- Foreign policy: It is that part of government activity that is outward-oriented; that is, that addresses, in contrast to domestic politics, problems that arise beyond borders (Marcel Merle's definition).

The legislative and executive powers are at the forefront of foreign policy makers, but they differ according to the nature of state systems.

- 3- International politics: are the foreign policies of states in their mutual interactions, in addition to their interactions with the international system as a whole, with international organizations, and with non-state social groups, in addition to the action of the international system and the domestic policies of all states (Joseph Frankl's definition).

As examples of international politics: participating in the Olympic Games – exporting oil through producing companies.

The study of international politics is more complex than the study of foreign policy because of the heterogeneity between the elements of the environment in which we live, as international politics seeks to obtain a greater content of violence, a high percentage of change and other characteristics.

International politics is also more dependent on international relations in non-political aspects, such as the economy (development, trade and aid), and in the meeting (blood ties between ruling families), as well as on the military side.

International policy and foreign policy differ in terms of elements, the elements of foreign policy are individuals, institutions and parties, while the elements of international policy are states, international organizations and other activist groups, and they differ in the element of analysis for each of them.

Concern with the relationship of international politics to international trade is only to the extent that governments use methods of economic threat, reward and punishment for political purposes, when governments promise certain countries to reduce tariffs in exchange for these countries allowing them to establish military bases on their territories.

4- International Order

Norman Barlford and George Lincoln define it as an arrangement of relations between states at a given time, and according to Letterlion, it consists of a set of regimes operating with a certain and distinct military, diplomatic, legal and economic function. "

It is characteristic of the international system that:

Totalitarianism: It was not possible to talk about an international system more than a century ago, but with the end of the Second World War, it can be said that the features and features of the international system began to appear and were the equal participation of all countries in an intensive network of permanent and global organizations first, the increase in the intensity of economic transactions second, the emergence of rapid communications in the field of media third, and the emergence of nuclear weapons and the results they brought in terms of international relations fourth.

Heterogeneity: What is meant by this system, which is based on a group of countries that belong in their internal systems to different values and ideologies that clash with great impact in determining their foreign policy. In this regard, researchers point to the stability that homogeneity leads to in the international system, and the threat that homogeneity poses to this stability.

The heterogeneity between countries is due to inequality among members of the international community. With the emergence of political and economic problems resulting from the phenomenon of decolonization and the entry of third world countries into the international stage, a large gap has emerged between the industrialized world and developing countries. In addition, inequality in power has been exacerbated by different cultures and civilizations. Racial differences and religions can be added, which makes it difficult to find a common language of understanding between countries, and even sometimes we find that cultural differences are difficult to overcome.

Interaction between units and rejection of isolation

The world has become a small village due to the revolution in the means of communication and the amazing development in the media. The full interconnection between its various parts was achieved, in addition to the fact that the development of means of transport, especially air transport, contributed in an interesting way to increasing the movement of interactions and communications between the various units of the international community, and the peoples were able to achieve very great benefits as a result.

Lack of international authority:

The nature of the international community is fundamentally different from the nature of the internal society. The internal society is a society organized for the existence of a government that imposes its authority on all its members voluntarily or spontaneously, while the international community lacks an instrument that imposes its authority on all its members. At a time when the international community is composed of states that are free in their destiny, the internal society is characterized by being accurately organized by the presence of a supreme authority to which all social groups are subject.

The crisis has brought the accountability of the activation of international law to the forefront in terms of the following:

- 1- that states have traditionally been the main subjects of public international law since the Middle Ages, called nation-states.
- 2- The idea of joining the law of the world is a voluntary act of the state, and this is still the case as we see in Chapter VII of the Charter of the United Nations regarding the intervention of the Security Council in issues of war and peace, when a state uses the right of veto, because the resolution is contrary to its interests, or by abstaining from voting.

For this, decision-makers seek to rely on the international decision to achieve their goals in two ways:

- 1- Work to legitimize their policies in order to obtain international acceptance, when national behavior fully conforms to the requirements of international law.
- 2- Working to use international law as a means to weaken the actions of the adversary.

Factors affecting international relations

Geography

The Russian-Ukrainian war brought to mind Mackinder's theory, known as the "heart of the world" theory, which says: Who rules Europe controls the heart of the world, who rules the heart of the world controls the island of the world, and who controls the island of the world and the heart of the world controls the world.

After the end of its Soviet era, Russia sought with all its strength to remain in control of Europe, especially Eastern Europe, and its allies such as Armenia, Georgia and Ukraine, and this comes according to the **realist school** that the goal is to defend its security against any military alliances such as NATO or the European Union, as well as for the glory it lost after the fall of the Soviet Union.

With regard to Ukraine, and from the point of view of geopolitics, during its development, countries seek to reach natural borders to achieve two goals: to obtain the largest area that can be controlled, and to try to reach borders that can be achieved by controlling them.

These countries seek to reach natural political borders for several factors, including: a political goal represented in achieving state hegemony over a larger area, achieving security in all its forms, and concluding agreements and treaties with neighboring countries.

This means that political boundaries are characterized by being unstable and can change and disappear, and if we see this in fact, and from the **historical approach**, we have Crimea as a model, which is the first sign of the Russian-Ukrainian conflict in the twenty-first century, and has roots in the past decades of the twentieth century.

Crimea as a model

Crimea lies north of the Black Sea; it is bounded to the east by the Sea of Azov. It has a population of two million according to the 2001 census¹, and in 2005, the number reached 1,994,300.

¹- Statistics of the Ukrainian government 2001: <http://2001.ukrcensus.gov.ua/eng/results/general/nationality/Crimea>

The word Crimea means "fortress" or "castle" in the Tatar language, and his fame was associated with the Ottomans during the existence of the state of the Crimean Tatar Khanate, which was established in 1430AD, and lasted more than three centuries before it was overthrown by Empress Catherine II in 1783AD, where it then began to displace large numbers of its Russian citizens there.

Its current capital is Simferopol, and its old name was "Aq Masjid", that is, the "White Mosque" in the language of the Crimean Tatars before the Russians seized it. Simferopol was once famous for its Crimean War in the 19th century. It remained of the utmost importance in the twentieth century because it contained a Russian naval base that was the only one of its kind in warm waters.

Its capital was once the city of "Bakhsh Sarai" when it was under the rule of the Tatar Khanates, and one of its important cities was the tourist city of Yalta (the Yalta Conference was held between the leaders of the Allies in World War II in February 1945, "Stalin, Roosevelt and Churchill"), while the city of Sevastopol was a port that housed the huge Soviet fleet, which became the subject of a dispute between Russia and Ukraine.

Ukraine–Russia conflict over Crimea

The emergence of the conflict between Russia and Ukraine was in stages as follows:

The first stage: Russia seized Crimea in the late eighteenth century 1783AD, when the armies of the Russian Empress Catherine the Great defeated the Crimean Tatars who were allied with the Ottomans, after several decades of wars.

The second stage: When Soviet leader Joseph Stalin decided in 1944 to expel the Tatars from the region for their alliance with the Nazis during World War II, and then returned to it again after the collapse of the Soviet Union, and they now constitute about 12 percent of its population.

The third stage: When Crimea became part of Ukraine in 1954, by a decision of the Soviet leader Nikita Khrushchev – of Ukrainian origin – he gave it to his native country. The decision had no practical effect during the Soviet era, but after the collapse and disintegration of the Soviet Union in 1991,

Crimea became part of independent Ukraine. Despite this, more than 60% of its population still consider themselves Russian².

Phase 4: In September 2008, Ukrainian Foreign Minister Volodymyr Oryzko accused Russia of granting Russian passports to citizens of Crimea, calling it a “real problem” given that Russia had declared military intervention abroad in order to protect Russian citizens³.

The fifth stage: On April 27, 2010, chaos and sharp debates broke out in the Ukrainian parliament due to the ratification by the Ukrainian parliament of the extension of the lease contract for the Russian naval base and military installations in Sevastopol, Crimea port until 2042, and the Russian State Duma also ratified the treaty.

Phase 6: At the end of 2013, Euromaidan protests began in Kiev to demand Ukraine's entry into the European Union after the government of President Viktor Yanukovich suspended the signing of the Association Agreement with the Union.

The pace of these protests increased with the beginning of 2014 and led to the killing of many protesters and government forces, as clashes between security forces and protesters flared starting on February 20. Amid those circumstances, Ukraine's lower house of parliament voted on February 22 to impeach President Yanukovich.

Seventh Stage: On February 27, 2014, armed men wearing de-identified military uniforms occupied facilities of importance in Crimea, including the Crimean parliament and two airports. Ukraine then accused Russia of interfering in its internal affairs.

On March 1, 2014, the Council of the Russian Federation unanimously approved Russian President Vladimir Putin's request to use Russian troops in Ukraine.

On March 2, 2014, the National Security Council of Ukraine summoned the entire Armed Forces Reserve Forces⁵.

²- About the first three phases, BBC: http://www.bbc.com/arabic/worldnews/2014/03/140301_crimea_facts

³- From AFP archive: <http://web.archive.org/web/20110521100144/http://afp.google.com/article/ALeqM5j57jsvObBZruGm0n7HhUA7rCG7nA>

⁴|||UNTRANSLATED_CONTENT_START||| - قناة الجزيرة:

<http://www.aljazeera.net/news/international/2014/3/1/%d8%b1%d9%88%d8%b3%d9%8a%d8%a7-%d8%aa%d8%aa%d9%87%d9%8a%d8%a3-%d9%84%d8%aa%d8%af%d8%ae%d9%84-%d8%b9%d8%b3%d9%83%d8%b1%d9%8a-%d9%81%d9%8a-%d8%a3%d9%88%d9%83%d8%b1%d8%a7%d9%86%d9%8a%d8%a7> |||UNTRANSLATED_CONTENT_END|||

⁵- Channel France 24: <http://www.france24.com/en/20140302-%8A%D8%A3%D9%88%D9%83%D8%B1%D8%A7%D9%86%D9%D8%A7-%D8%A7%D8%B3%D8%AA%D8%AF%D8%B9%D8%A7%D8%A1-%8A%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%AC%D9%D8%B4-%D8>

On March 3, 2014, the head of the Black Sea Fleet gave the Ukrainian government until 4 a.m. to hand over Crimea to Russia.

Eighth stage: The Crimean Parliament announced the organization of a referendum on March 16, 2014, which resulted in the declaration of the establishment of the Republic of Crimea on March 18, 2014, which was approved by 95%, that the Republic of Crimea joins in favor of the Union of Republics of Russia.

In Turkish President Recep Tayyip Erdogan's repeated speech before and during this latest war, he pointed out that the Russian-Ukrainian conflict would not have returned if the West had not been silent about the events in Crimea⁶, stressing that Turkey does not recognize the Russian presence and the subordination of Crimea to Russia⁷.

The director of the Moscow Middle East Institute, Evgeny Satanovsky, points out that Erdogan is adhering to the Turkish historical right to Crimea, as well as in the Turkish curriculum, which indicates the existence of this⁸.

An observer of Erdogan's position, and the confirmed news that Ukraine has been supplied with Turkish drones known as "Bayraktar", will know that Turkey has indirectly entered the arena of conflict, even if the latter states that this is not military support between the two countries⁹.

We do not forget the rapid Turkish position regarding the activation of the International Maritime Agreement, by not allowing the passage of any military supplies through the Bosphorus and the Dardanelles, and this decision, according to military analysts, constitutes a negative for the Russian move in the international sea lanes¹⁰.

The Turkish position comes in what is known in the science of international relations as the "balance of power", where the researcher believes that it means that there is a third country carrying the balance so that it achieves parity in a battle between two parties¹¹.

[A7% D8% AD%8A % D8% AA%8A % D9% D8% A7% D8% B7% D9-%8A% D8% B1% D9% 88% D8% B3% D9% D8% A7-% D8% AA% D8% AF% D8% AE%D9%/84](https://al-ain.com/article/erdogan-silence-war-ukraine)

⁶- Source: Al Ain News Platform, retrieved from the link: <https://al-ain.com/article/erdogan-silence-war-ukraine>

⁷- Source: Russia Today, retrieved from <https://ar.rt.com/rc80>

⁸- Source: Russia Today, retrieved from <https://ar.rt.com/rc10>

⁹- Source: Russia Today, retrieved from the link: <https://ar.rt.com/sjf3>

¹⁰- Source: German DW channel, retrieved from <https://p.dw.com/p/47npe>

¹¹- Source: The Book of Principles of International Relations, p. 224

Returning to the relationship of geographical location as a factor in international relations in the Ukraine war, we note that the current Ukrainian president's demand for Blah to join the European Union opened fire on him and his neighbors, such as Moldova, and others who demanded the European Union to quickly annex them, lest the encroachment on them come after Russia ends the Ukraine war.

This is what is currently pushing the European Union to push for military and economic reinforcements to prevent a defeat in Ukraine, but at the same time the European continent suffers from a lack of energy supplies as a result of Russian President Putin's imposition of strict measures to sell natural gas in Russian rubles, and this makes the Europeans hope that Turkey will make efforts in the short term to calm and end the war.

Primary Resources

The war has refrained from the size of the confusion suffered by the units of the international system, which consists of the primary and secondary players who contribute to the formation of international relations. This brings to mind the linkage of what is happening **with the theory of the game**, as Thomas Schilling explained that this theory is concerned with situations in which the best behavior of each party depends on its ability to predict what the other party will do, and this means distinguishing between games of strategy and games of chance¹².

This war revealed the world's need for food security¹³, and alarm was raised in many Arab countries that are witnessing the famine of Yemen by the World Food Program, which warned of the shortage of food supplies of wheat as a result of the Russian-Ukrainian war¹⁴, or countries that are witnessing a rise in prices, such¹⁵ as Egypt, as stated by their officials as a result of the decline in their stocks of wheat, in which Russia and Ukraine sit globally.

¹²- Source: The Book of Principles of International Relations, p. 125

¹³- Source: The Book of Principles of International Relations, p. 143

¹⁴|||UNTRANSLATED_CONTENT_START||| - المصدر: قناة سكاى نيوز عربية، تم الاسترداد من الرابط - <https://www.skynewsarabia.com/middle-east/1504292-%D9%84%D9%87%D9%8A%D8%A8-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%AD%D8%B1%D8%A8-%D8%A7%D9%94%D9%88%D9%83%D8%B1%D8%A7%D9%86%D9%8A%D8%A7-%D9%8A%D8%B5%D9%84-%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%8A%D9%85%D9%86-%D9%88%D9%84%D9%85%D8%A7%D8%B0%D8%A7%D8%9F> |||UNTRANSLATED_CONTENT_END|||

¹⁵- Source: Al Arabiya, retrieved from <https://ara.tv/9svpt>

On the other hand, the continent of Europe suffers from weak energy supplies as a result of Russian conditions on the purchase of energy, and it is made more difficult that the shipping costs of natural gas from America will not be at the usual price in the market due to increased shipping costs.

As for Qatar, its Energy Minister Saad Al-Kaabi said that his country will not be able to meet the needs of the European continent¹⁶ in the near future, since it needs to formulate long-term contracts at specific prices, which the Europeans do not want.

On the side of Yemen, and after stopping the export of gas from it as a result of the events of Yemen 2015, US officials sought to negotiate with Yemeni officials¹⁷ and under the umbrella of the Arab coalition to resume the export of natural gas from the Balhaf area in Shabwa to European countries again after a years-long interruption as a result of security imbalances suffered by the natural gas export areas, in addition to other factors revealed by one of the Wikileaks documents¹⁸.

The United States of America also sought to push the UAE and Saudi Arabia towards increasing oil production, but the latter two refused to do so, as they were indirectly involved in the Russian-Ukrainian war. This brings history back to the first use of oil as a political card. October 1973 was welcomed when the Arab oil-producing countries stopped exporting oil to the West, which made oil prices increase. Also¹⁹, do not forget that the Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries "OPEC" reached in the meetings of "OPEC Plus" an agreement that included a compromise in the amount of daily oil production between Russia and Saudi Arabia, and then the UAE.

On the Russian side, Russia is one of the continental (landlocked) countries. One of the most important objectives of this war is to reach the Azov War, which links its Crimean peninsula with its southern coasts. Therefore, Russia recognized the independence of the Luhansk and Donetsk regions, which are coastal areas overlooking the Sea of Azov. Russia is still counting on the overthrow of the city of Mariupol by itself to complete control the coastal strip of Azov, which contains a huge stock of fish wealth of more than

¹⁶- Source: EuroNews, retrieved from <https://arabic.euronews.com/2022/02/22/qatar-no-single-country-can-replace-russian-gas-supply-to-europe>

¹⁷- Source: South Today, retrieved from <http://www.aljanoobalyoum.net/54595/>

¹⁸- Source: Al Masdar Online, retrieved from <https://almasdaronline.com/articles/72277>

¹⁹- Source: The Book of Principles of International Relations, p. 147

80 species, in addition to the presence of oil in those places. In the event of a referendum in the regions overlooking the Sea of Azov in order to join Russia, this means strengthening Russia's economic power, and coming up with more financial gains than it lost during this war.

After all, this war is like a zero-sum game, it pays off when the other loses.

Economic factor.

Many international companies have played a role in strengthening economic sanctions against Russia in this war, including Visa and MasterCard, which have decided to stop their services with Russian banks, and swift, the international organization for cash transfers, has stopped financial transfers to and from Russia, which has been an obstacle to economic exchange between Russia and many countries of the world.

However, according to Putin's statements, since the 2014 Crimea crisis, Russia has prepared to face this type of sanctions, and this indicates the ageing of the global system, which is suffering from economic blows due to the rise of China and Russia to the forefront of the world again.

The "Russian-Ukrainian" war has put the international community in an awkward position in which it appears only as the appearance of spectators in the stadium stands. Aid has been largely limited to the humanitarian side of Ukrainian refugees, with caution against providing military aid to Kiev, and only imposing economic sanctions on Russia instead of the military intervention denied by NATO forces. This made the Ukrainian president open the door to recruiting all fighters from around the world to fight Russia, which made Russia respond with a similar step.

Observing the scene from the comparisons between Russian and Ukrainian military power put forward by many media outlets, he will find statistics at first glance indicating that victory is Russia's ally.

The phenomenon of international cooperation in the shadow of war

The international arena has witnessed a division between supporters and opponents of Russia's war against Ukraine. At the same time, there is a team that refrained from expressing its opinion on what happened. The Security Council, given that the five

permanent members and veto-wielding powers have failed to reach a condemnation regarding the war due to the Russian presence in the Security Council, the countries opposing the United Nations General Assembly sought to extract a straw-like resolution condemning Russia. This indicates the usual failure of these international organizations to hold collective security accountable.

It is noticeable in that scene that the phenomenon of international cooperation was manifested in the exchange of interests between the countries that stood in favor of the warring parties. As an example, we find that the UAE refrains from voting against Russia in exchange for a Russian vote in favor of including the Houthis on the Security Council blacklist.

At the same time, Iran responds, but this time through former President Ahmadinejad, who supported Ukraine, in response to Russia's vote in the Security Council on the decision to include the Houthis on the terrorist list.

As examples, it is noted that this war will change the parameters of international politics from bipolar to multipolar, in light of the failure of Western powers to end the Russian attack on Ukraine.

Sources

Tawfiq, Saad. (2010). Principles of International Relations. Baghdad, Iraq: Al-Atiq Book Manufacturing Company

Official website of the Ukrainian government

Al Jazeera

Channel France 24

Sky News Arabia

Al Arabiya

Al Ain News Platform

BBC

AFP

EuroNews

German DW Channel

Russia Today channel?

Al-Janoub newspaper today

Al Masdar Online Newspaper